

Forced Labour and Forced Marriage as a Form of Modern Slavery in Today's World

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Abstract:- The research paper aims at creating an overview article on the topic of slavery in the Modern World especially focusing on Forced Labour and Children's Marriages. The research paper investigates sources and draws conclusion on the topic. Text synthesis, analysis, comparison, and other methods are used.

Keywords:- Forced Labour, Children Marriages, Modern Slavery.

I. INTRODUCTION

This research article summarizes current findings regarding slavery in the Modern World. Unfortunately, more people are involved in slavery and its forms in today's World than there have ever been before.

We shall not expect any slavery in modern society; however, the slavers found a new way to bind people to them. Unfortunately, many governments and officials do not desire to change anything regarding this topic.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The number of victims of contemporary slavery has skyrocketed over the past five years. According to predictions made for the World in 2016, an additional 10 million people will live under slavery in the year 2021. Women and children are still disproportionately affected by this problem (International Labor Organisation, 2022).

Modern slavery takes many forms; however, two most notable are:

- Forced labor,
- Forced marriage mainly manifests in child marriages.

The private sector is responsible for 86% of all instances of forced labor that can be found today. Only 23% of all forced labor is employed in industries that involve commercial sexual exploitation. In contrast, the remaining 63% of all forced labor is used in sectors other than commercial sexual exploitation. Women and girls make up almost four out of every five victims of sexual exploitation for commercial gain (International Labor Organisation, 2022).

The International Labour Organization defines forced labor as any task or service exacted from any person under the threat of any penalty and for which that person has not voluntarily volunteered. In other words, a person is considered to be performing forced labor when they are

being coerced into performing a task or service (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Technische Zusammenarbeit, 2008).

Forced Labour and slavery, in general, may be enabled by causes such as (Homeland Security, 2022):

- Unstable immigration status
- Language barriers
- Poverty and lack of basic needs like food, shelter, and safety
- The psychological effects of a recent or past trauma
- Lack of social support systems like friends, family, and community
- Physical or developmental disabilities.

Forced slavery takes, however, other forms, as well (Unseen UK, 2022):

- Forced Labour of any kind,
- Forced Labour in factories for less than a minimum wage,
- Debt Bondage,
- Child exploitation,
- Criminal exploitation,
- Domestic servitude,
- Sexual exploitation,
- Descent-based slavery,
- Forced begging,
- Agriculture and Mining works.

For more than a century, it has been unclear what criteria should be used to determine whether "former" enslaved people are still being subjected to slavery-related abuse and whether additional action is required to end this practice in regions of the World where slavery was formally abolished. Still, enslaved people continued to live in the same places, as dependent on their "former" owners as they were before (Dottridge, 2005).

This is true in areas where slavery was nominally abolished, but enslaved people continued to live were formerly enslaved and their descendants have faced discrimination and brutality on every continent due to their position. Despite this, a renewed focus on countries such as Mauritania and Niger, as well as more recent cases, has resulted from a resurgent interest in slavery (Dottridge, 2005).

Over the last five years, Western media outlets have drawn attention to the plight of Dinka women and children in Sudan who were kidnapped from their homes and forced to live and work in Arabic-speaking communities that abducted them; teenage migrants from Mali who were beaten for not working hard enough on cocoa farms in Côte d'Ivoire; and pre-pubescent boys and girls working full-time

as live-in servants, both at home and abroad (Dottridge, 2005).

The media in Sub-Saharan Africa has covered instances like these, and a wide range of other events deemed harsh by journalists. On the other side, little is being done by governments or others in positions of authority to prevent or eradicate misuse, demonstrating that individuals in positions of responsibility do not yet understand what they should stop. As a result, this most likely represents the public's disparate viewpoints (Dottridge, 2005).

It is estimated that 1 in 200 people around the World is currently enslaved in some form. This amounts to more than 45 million people who are actively working somewhere. Shackles and ships sailing across oceans are two familiar images that come to mind when one thinks of slavery. In addition, we frequently feel that the custom is no longer commonly used. The vast majority of scholars agree that during the 15th and 19th centuries, roughly 13 million people were kidnapped and forced into slavery after being sold into servitude (Beuk, 2020).

It is estimated that more than 40.3 million individuals live in modern-day slavery. This indicates that a much larger number of individuals are held in slavery today compared to the 400 years that the majority of people believe slavery was practiced (Beuk, 2020).

Enslaved people will almost certainly spend their lives in servitude until they are uncovered and set free. People will be able to recognize and report cases of modern slavery if they are familiar with its signals. The following are some examples of common warning signs that one may be involved in the slavery of any form (Beuk, 2020):

- Exhibiting both physical and mental manifestations of dread
- Does not have the ability to travel to any location of their choosing freely; does not possess identity or other necessary documentation

- There is a strict no-personal-items policy.
- Is too timid to attempt to approach you
- It would appear that a third party is controlling what is happening there.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology includes a review of sources available online. Methods of study, analysis, compilation, and description are used. The primary purpose of this article is to point out the problem of slavery in the modern World and the fact that slavery is, in fact, increasing even if we live in a modern developed World in which slavery in any form shall be, on the other hand, decreasing as society develops itself.

Official sources such as International Labour Organisation, Special Action Programme to Combat Forced Labour or statistical database Statista are used for assessing the data.

IV. SLAVERY IN THE MODERN WORLD IN THE CHARTS

Slavery in the modern World is investigated from the point of view of forced Labour and the point of view of forced marriage.

A. Forced labour

Forced Labour takes part in a form such as sexual exploitation, working in construction and agriculture, or domestic work. Forced Labour is a problem around the World, but the main emphasis shifted from Africa to Asia.

The estimated annual profit of forced Labour is highest in Asia and Pacific's region followed by Developed economies such as the USA and the EU.

Chart 1: Estimated profit from forced Labour.

Source: own based on Special Action Programme to Combat Forced Labour, 2022.

It is a surprise to state that the annual profit from forced Labour in Africa is approximately USD 13,1 bil., however in the developed countries such as the USA and the EU it is USD 46,9 bil. In the case of the EU, it is nearly 3,5 times more than in Africa (Special Action Programme to Combat Forced Labour, 2022).

From the point of view of the number of enslaved people in respective countries, the most enslaved people were in India, then in China, Pakistan, North Korea, Nigeria, Indonesia, DR Congo, and Russia. Of course, these numbers are only estimated since it is literally impossible to discover all the cases.

Country	Est. number of enslaved people	Total population	Ratio Est. enslaved people:total population
India	7,989,000	1,380,004,385	0,58 %
China	3,864,000	1,439,323,776	0,26 %
Pakistan	3,186,000	220,892,340	1,44 %
North Korea	2,640,000	25,778,816	10,2 %
Indonesia	1,220,000	273,523,615	0,44 %
DR Congo	1,045,000	89,561,403	1,17 %
Russia	794,000	145,934,462	0,54 %
Total TOP 7	20 738 000	3,575,018,797	0,58 %

Table 1: Country with the highest number of forced laborers or enslaved people in other ways.

Source: own based on Statista 2021a and Worldometer, 2022.

As of estimated 40-50 million slaves around the Globe, approximately half of them are in the TOP 7 countries. If the ratio of the total population and the estimated number of enslaved people is calculated, it is around 0,58 % of the population in total.

It is viable to note that the numbers mentioned above are rough estimations since it is impossible to predict the actual number of people caught in forced slavery – labour.

B. Forced marriages

Forced marriages are, unfortunately, not uncommon, even in developed countries. In total, as of 2020, the countries with the most child marriages in the World were India, Bangladesh, Nigeria, Ethiopia and Brazil, Pakistan, and Indonesia. The following chart shows the countries with the highest number of child marriages in 2020.

Chart: absolute numbers of child marriages in 2020 in respective countries

Source: own based on Statista, 2021b.

It is necessary to fight any forms of enslaving, not only forced Labour or forced marriages. Also, it is essential to provide excellent and much-needed help to people who have to work (forced Labour) or have been married against their will (forced marriages or children marriages).

In many cases, large rings and groups of criminals (organized crimes) are involved, and it is not possible to break out or escape these criminal groups or rings without sufficient help and protection from police or similar government agencies.

V. FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

It is possible to conclude the following conclusions:

- The most affected region by forced Labour in Asia and the Pacific Region,
- Forced Labour in the EU and the USA is higher than in Africa and Latin America together,
- Social systems are not prepared to fight slavery efficiently – even in developed countries,
- Developed countries fail in protecting people (citizens and non-citizens) from slavery and modern forms of exploitation, and this is a violation of fundamental human rights,
- As of an estimated 40-50 million slaves around the Globe, approximately half of them (around 20 mil.) live in the so-called "TOP 7 slaves" countries,
- If the ratio of the total population and estimated number of enslaved people is calculated it is around 0,58 % of the population in total.
- It does not depend on if the country is "developed" or "developing", the slavery is spread in both categories of countries.
- Forced marriage is a severe offense to one's privacy, especially if children are involved; the countries with the highest absolute number of child marriages are India, Bangladesh, Nigeria, Pakistan, Indonesia, Mexico, DR Congo, and others.
- More than 15 000 000 child marriages are documented in India as of 2020, far more than in Bangladesh (2nd) or Nigeria (3rd).
- There can be seen relations between forced labor and marriage – countries with the highest number of documented forced laborers and forced marriages are nearly the same – especially mentioned countries such as India, Pakistan, Nigeria, Indonesia, or DR Congo, as seen in both charts regarding forced Labour as well as forced marriages numbers.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

It is much needed to stop any form of slavery in the modern World, for instance, by doing the following:

- Support anti-slavery organisations such as Amnesty International,
- Support underprivileged children who lives in poor conditions,
- Do not buy anything sold by children – especially in South Asia; if parents see that children bring cash home

and are successful, they will send their children out to sell small products such as lighters or sunglasses again,

- Do not be indifferent,
- Encourage government, police, and security agencies to fight against slavery and criminal rings that enslaves people,
- Change the environment and culture-related traditions, such as in the case of children's marriages.

REFERENCES

- [1.] International Labor Organisation, 2022. Fifty million people worldwide in modern slavery. (online). (quot. 22.11.2022). Available from: [https://www.ilo.org/global/about-the-ilo/newsroom/news/WCMS_855019/lang-en/index.htm#:~:text=GENEVA%20\(ILO%20News\)%20%20E2%80%93%20Fifty,were%20trapped%20in%20forced%20marriage](https://www.ilo.org/global/about-the-ilo/newsroom/news/WCMS_855019/lang-en/index.htm#:~:text=GENEVA%20(ILO%20News)%20%20E2%80%93%20Fifty,were%20trapped%20in%20forced%20marriage).
- [2.] Deutsche Gesellschaft für Technische Zusammenarbeit, 2008. Forced Labour and Trafficking in Persons. (online). (quot. 22.11.2022). Available from: <https://www.oecd.org/dac/gender-development/44896368.pdf>
- [3.] Homeland Security, 2022. What is Forced Labor. (online). (quot. 22.11.2022). Available from: <https://www.dhs.gov/blue-campaign/forced-labor>
- [4.] Unseen UK, 2022. Website. (online). (quot. 22.11.2022). Available from: <https://www.unseenuk.org/about-modern-slavery/types-of-modern-slavery/>
- [5.] Dottridge, M., 2005. Types of Forced Labour and Slavery-like Abuse Occurring in Africa Today in: Cahiers d'études africaines (2005), p. 689-712. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4000/etudesafriaines.14968>.
- [6.] Beuk, E., 2020. What Is Modern Day Slavery? Examples, Locations, Causes & Facts. (online). (quot. 22.11.2022). Available from: <https://liberatechildren.org/blog/what-is-modern-day-slavery>.
- [7.] Special Action Programme to Combat Forced Labour, 2022. Profits and poverty: The economics of forced labour. (online). (quot. 22.11.2022). Available from: <https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/forced-labour/statistics/lang-en/index.htm>.
- [8.] Statista, 2021a. Modern Slavery Is A Brutal Reality Worldwide. (online). (quot. 22.11.2022). Available from: <https://www.statista.com/chart/4937/modern-slavery-is-a-brutal-reality-worldwide/>
- [9.] Worldometer, 2022. Countries in the world by population. (online). (quot. 22.11.2022). Available from: <https://www.worldometers.info/world-population/population-by-country/>
- [10.] Statista, 2021b. Countries with the highest absolute numbers of child marriages as of 2020. (online). (quot. 22.11.2022). Available from: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1228332/highest-absolute-number-of-girl-brides-by-country/>